

To,
The Editor-in-Chief,
International Journal of Food Sciences and Nutrition

Subject: Manuscript submission

Dear Sir/ Madam,

I am hereby submitting a manuscript of research paper entitled “**Effect of geographical location and types of flora on physico-chemical, elemental and organoleptic properties of honey samples**” by Supriya D. Kamble, Asmita M. Acharya, Ajay K. Sharma and Akshaya K. Sahoo. Honey is a natural sweetener and highly nutritious traditional medicine. Composition and quality of honey vary according to several factors such as geographical origin, climacteric condition, type of flora, packaging and storage condition. The present study explores the physico-chemical, elemental and organoleptic properties of 11 honey samples of different flora collected from different Indian geographical sources. This research findings will be extremely useful for academicians, researchers and commercial stakeholders.

Kindly consider our manuscript for publication in your esteemed journal. Looking for a positive reply.

With best regards,

Sincerely yours,
Prof. Dr. A. K. Sahoo
Department of Food Science and Technology,
Shivaji University, Kolhapur, India